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Isabel Oliveira Abreu is a dedicated researcher pursuing her PhD in Environmental Toxicology and Contamination at the University of Porto. She focuses her research on investigating the impacts of pollutants on aquatic organism development and explores innovative early-warning techniques, such as behavioural assessment. With a master's degree in Toxicology and Environmental Contamination, throughout her academic journey, she actively engaged in diverse research projects and outreach initiatives, demonstrating her commitment to advancing scientific knowledge and addressing pressing environmental issues.

DISRUPTIVE BEHAVIOUR: IMPACT OF PESTICIDES ON NATIVE BEES

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Abstract

The impact of pesticides on bees has raised some concern among scientists and environmentalists. Pesticides pose a global threat to bee populations. Neonicotinoids and organophosphates disrupt bee behaviour, impairing navigation, foraging, and reproduction. Even sublethal doses weaken bees, affecting their survival and pollination efficiency. These disruptions harm plant reproduction and jeopardise the essential bee-plant relationship. The cumulative effects of pesticides and other stressors challenge bee populations and the critical ecosystem services they provide. Many pesticide compounds and bee species remain understudied. This study examined the potential sublethal effects of fenpyroximate on the behaviour of native bees in the Caatinga biome. Bees from the species *Melipona quadrifasciata* were exposed to sublethal doses of fenpyroximate, a commonly used fungicide in the Caatinga region, under controlled conditions for 24 hours: 0.028 µg/bee (2.5% of the recommended field application dose) and 0.56 µg/bee (50% of the recommended field application dose). After exposure, bee behaviour was recorded for 5 minutes, and the following parameters were analysed: percentage of time moving, average speed, average speed while moving, travelled distance, meandering, and explored area. Our findings show significant behavioural changes at 0.56 µg/bee. The most pronounced effects were observed in speed and explored area, while no significant changes were detected in parameters such as the percentage of time moving or meandering. This study underscores the importance of incorporating behavioural assays in bee toxicity testing. Although no immediate mortality was observed at the tested doses, fenpyroximate impacted bee behaviour. These findings support the use of behavioural tests as a valuable tool for assessing the sublethal effects of pesticides.

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